

HYDROPHILIZATION OF PET USING DBD PLASMA

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Introduction

Our work utilizes a parallel-plate non-thermal plasma dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) system worked at medium pressure in dry air or nitrogen gas to change the surface characterization polyethylene terephthalate (PET) non-woven fabric. The surface modification of PET fabric was determined by water contact angle (WCA), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and wettability analysis.

Schematic representation of DBD reactor

Results and Discussion

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